

THE IMMERSION METHOD AS AN EFFECTIVE METHOD FOR LEARNING AND TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6496814>

Jabborov Mirsaid

*SamSIFL, International language and literature
Second course*

Yakhyoyev Shermukhammad

*SamSIFL, International language and literature
Second course*

Abstract: *This article deals with the effective way of teaching and learning English language as a foreign language. The article represents the strategies for learning English, how to pick the right strategy and where to begin. It is analyzed the Immersion method and all aspects that will be investigated during the learning process.*

Keyword: *immersion, common language, function, English-speaking environment, innovative, modern.*

English is unambiguously the most generally spoken on the planet, so there are numerous ways and strategies to learn it. From books or over the span of ordinary correspondence, all alone or with a tutor, in a specialized school or through the Internet – the decision, for this situation, relies upon the capacities and inclinations of every specific learner.

What is the fastest course to consummate English? Numerous individuals who need to learn English rapidly are searching for this alternate route. On the Internet, it can be discovered tips and deceives that each learner can undoubtedly remember for his or her stockpile of preparing apparatuses. However, how great it is to track down the unparalleled right technique with which learners can rapidly and effectively master a foreign language. This issue was analyzed, and it was found out that the shortest way from the point “zero level” to the point “independent user” exists. Here is one of the best strategies for learning English. It has been probably known and even tried at least one of learners. Try to pick the strategy that is ideal for the students and figure out how to utilize it viably.

The Immersion Method is likewise called the common language learning strategy. This technique, as is obvious from “immersion”, accommodates the making of an alleged “linguistic environment” around oneself. As such, the

learners need to encircle themselves with English from all sides. This technique does not simply assist you with learning the language, it assists you with intuition in it. Learning English submersion changes your perspective to that of native English speakers. Likewise, utilizing this strategy, you by one way or another come into contact with the English language consistently. This is significant: a few investigations show that while rehearsing an hour daily will likewise deliver a few outcomes, it is hard to draw near to the level of a local speaker along these lines. Immersion has demonstrated a compelling replacement to past language showing approaches of traditional grammar-translation methods and the audiolingual methods for the 1960s and informative techniques for the 1970s. The focal quality of immersion is the instructing of language substance and culture in mix, without the utilization of the learner's first language. Students are encouraged a language that they at first do not comprehend through the utilization of an assortment of setting signs given by the educator.

How can it function? Consider how little children figure out how to speak. A newly born child does not yet know any language, he is encircled from all sides by endless discourse. Gradually he learns: he pays attention to what others are saying and how notices them, recalls words. Then, at that point the kid starts to see how these words are consolidated into discourse structures. He rehashes singular words, then, at that point phrases, at last starts to construct sentences and speak easily. This is the reason the inundation technique is known as the "regular" strategy: the more English is spoken around you, the simpler and quicker you will figure out how to communicate in English. This method might be suggested for the individuals who live in an Englishspeaking country, experiences issues recollecting punctuation rules, needs to begin conveying in English as quickly as time permits, learns language material better by ear and communicated in language. To utilize this showing technique, you need to encircle yourself with English however much as could reasonably be expected. On the off chance that you live in an Englishspeaking country, you are extremely lucky. Also, here's the means by which you can guarantee yourself extra every day contact with the English language:

- Change the interface language of your gadgets, informal organizations and locales you visit as often as possible to English. O Join a club or group of English lovers, on the web or disconnected. Discover a vested party so you have something to discuss.

- On the off chance that you are in school, college or other instructive organization, attempt to communicate in English with your kindred understudies as frequently as could really be expected.
- Watch films and TV shows in English. On the off chance that you don't comprehend all that is said on the screen, you are as yet learning undetected. ○ Watch the news and pay attention to the radio, buy in to papers or magazines in English. Let the English language be heard in the first part of the day.

The method looks to “accelerate” language securing by giving most extreme openness while a sympathetic methodology assists with building certainty which as per Sharpe (1992) is a significant factor in effective current language educating, just as being a significant factor in the distinction in the office with which grownups and kids can become familiar with a subsequent language.

REFERENCES:

1. Reyhner, John (1998): What's Immersion Education
2. Reyhner, John: Immersion Education, NABE News August 1, 1998, vol.21, No. 8
3. Sharpe, K. (1992). Communication, Culture, Context, Confidence: The Four 'Cs' in
4. Sharpe, K. (1992). Communication, Culture, Context, Confidence: The four 'Cs' in Primary Modern Language Teaching, ALL Language Teaching Journal, 6.
5. Cummins, J. (1998). Immersion education for the millennium: What have we learned from 30 years of research on second language immersion? In M. R. Childs & R. M. Bostwick (Eds.) Learning through two languages: Research and practice. Second Katoch Gakuen International Symposium on Immersion and Bilingual Education (pp. 34-47).